

Table A1. Identity of the isolates G4, GL01, and GL02 based on the similarity between samples sequences and the sequences in genebank

Isolate code	Accession number (NCBI)	Identity	ITS fragment length (base pairs)	Homology	BLAST bit score
G4	KX092000.1	<i>Ganoderma boninense</i>	655	98.92%	1085
GL01	JQ520182.1	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	636	99.83%	1098
GL02	KT906368.1	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	638	99.83%	1098